

Open Scholarship Garden

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Purpose

The [Open Scholarship Framework at SFU](#) has an ambitious goal: to make open practices the norm across disciplines and career stages at the university level. This means that the policies that we're implementing need to address the peculiarities, challenges and opportunities that each research endeavour encompasses. In that sense, we like to think that we are cultivating an open scholarship garden: sometimes an open practice is deeply rooted in a certain way of producing knowledge, sometimes it's a pollinator connecting different groups or ideas, or sometimes it's perceived as an invasive weed. In this session, we want to bring participants together to imagine this garden with us, what the Canadian open ecosystem looks like right now across disciplines, what care this garden needs to flourish and persist, and what it could become if we get it right.

Outcome

At the end of this session, we will have reflected about the impacts, challenges and opportunities derived from different aspects of open scholarship. We will have one or more panels with a collectively constructed drawing of our current or desired open scholarship garden. With that, we hope to combine diverse perspectives across disciplines and gain clarity about the expectations and points of friction of the open science and open scholarship community in Canada.

Process

The booth will be composed of one or more poster boards and "blank canvases". Participants will be invited to imagine growing this ecosystem by drawing on the boards, adding plants, animals, and tools, and reflecting on the benefits and challenges of each component of an open scholarship framework. We will guide participants' thinking with prompts, encouraging them to reflect on their own experiences. When the session ends, we will document what's on each panel and

share it under an open license, acknowledging the contributions of the participants.

Session plan

Before the session:

1. Prepare a list of keywords, sentences, concepts and ideas related to open scholarship. Make sure to have a diverse range of concepts, including good and bad things about open scholarship, entry-level and advanced concepts, and things that are not open scholarship but could somehow be related to it.
 - a. Print them out or write them down on paper and cut them separately.
 - b. Make sure to print/write them using large, legible fonts.
 - c. See some examples on Appendix A
2. Prepare images that could be stucked to the panel instead of drawing. This is important to account for accessibility and to get people inspired. These images can be printed images, stickers, or magazine extracts, for example.
3. Have a good range of colour pencils and other materials to be used by participants.
4. Have the instructions written down and printed in legible fonts. See an example on Appendix B.
5. Have any other “plus” and incentives prepared. For example, during the 1st Canadian Open Science and Open Scholarship Conference, we used a spinning wheel with chocolate bars as prizes, and extra stickers to give away.

Setting up the space:

1. Put up a poster board / large paper in a place where people can write and draw pictures on. This can be adapted to a set of regular-sized papers on a table.
2. Make initial drafts on the drawing area to delineate the space. Draw things like the Sun, some clouds and the floor line.
3. Decorate the space with garden-themed images/stickers/objects. Adding soundscape is a plus but it depends heavily on the ambient where the activity will happen.

4. Spread the keywords on a table in a way that people can read them and start thinking about what they want to draw.
5. Have the colour pencils organized in pencil holders / cups near the keywords, such that people can easily identify the colours they need and grab a pencil to start drawing.
6. Set up any other devices/incentives.

During the session:

1. Invite people over to draw on the board and contribute to the open scholarship garden.
2. Be clear about the objective of the activity, and that you are looking for their own experience and perception.
3. Prompt them with examples, such as:
 - a. “What is a practice that is deeply rooted in your area?”
 - b. “Which concept you think is the seed for something else?”
 - c. “What is the garbage of open scholarship in your experience? What is something you had to deal with that was getting in the way of your beautiful garden of research practice?”
 - d. “Is there any concept on this table that is a consequence of something that is already depicted on the board?”
4. Engage them in any other activity / incentives / games.

After the session:

1. Take pictures of the final board, making sure to capture the details and to take notes about people’s comments.
2. Unassemble the space, collect the garbage, and thank remaining participants.

What if...?

... only a few people show up? Draw along with the ones that do show up!

... a lot of people shows up? Encourage people to work in pairs/groups.

... people lose interest? Engage in a conversation and ignore the drawing.

APPENDIX

A) Example list of terms, ideas and concepts to be used in the activity:

Reproducibility	Transparency
Open Access	Open Data
Open Peer Review	Open Educational Resources
Open Source Software	FAIR Principles
Indigenous Data Governance	Community Science
Research Integrity	Responsible Research and Innovation
Open Metrics / Alternative Metrics	Preprints
Open Hardware	Community-Driven Research
Archive code	Use inclusive language in any documentation
License research outputs openly	Register study protocols in advance
Share negative results	Use persistent identifiers
Provide detailed metadata	Document data processing steps clearly
Engage with local community in research design	Archive datasets in open repositories
Use open lab notebooks	Train researchers in open science practices
Advocate for open science in your institution	Acknowledge contributors accurately
Ensure accessibility of research outputs	Use non-proprietary file formats
Publish in open access journals	Cite data and software properly
Participate in open peer review processes	Fund open source software and infrastructure
Funding	Human resources

Training in open scholarship
best practices

Informed decisions

Cite preprints

Social inequalities

Open-shaming

Scooping

Biased sampling

Gate-keeping

Centralized power

Recognition

Tenure & Promotion

EDIA

Social justice

Reduce research waste

Better informed public policies

Social injustice

Article Processing Charges

Bias

P-hacking

Bibliodiversity

Decentralized power

Incentives

Research Assessment Metrics

B) Rules document example

Open Scholarship Garden

Rules:

1. Grab a concept on the table
2. Think about how this concept would contribute to or harm our open scholarship garden
3. Draw **one** element on the garden that represents this concept
4. Spin the wheel for a chance of getting a chocolate bar!

Open Scholarship Garden; Rules: 1. Grab a concept on the table; 2. Think about how this concept would contribute to or harm our open scholarship garden; 3. Draw one element on the garden that represents this concept; 4. Spin the wheel for a chance of getting a chocolate bar!

C) Documentation of the Open Scholarship Garden session held at the 1st Canadian Open Science and Open Scholarship Conference

